

ENGLISH LEARNING EXPERIENCE BY ADULT BEGINNERS

AN EMOTIONAL CHALLENGE

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this article is to verify emotional responses of adult beginners in an English Language class planned using the Task-Based English Teaching framework within the Communicative Approach to Language Teaching. As it is considered the main approach to foreign language teaching, we aim to discuss its effectiveness towards providing students the best scenario to language learning. We have conducted an English class based on the premises of the approach to adult learners who had never had contact with a foreign language before. We have encountered a set of negative and positive emotions related to the experience, especially when the learners considered the environment and the designed oral tasks. Afterwards, these emotions were categorized by Russell's circumplex model according to the primary emotions and their activations. Finally, we have considered McLellan's sweet spot model and how Design could help easing the activation of the encountered negative emotions.

Keywords: design, experience, emotion, language & learning.

INTRODUCTION

In this article, we intend to firstly discuss what the communicative approach to teaching English – the most popular approach used by language courses in Brazil – is and how it is connected to experience. Based on emotional experiences, our main goal is to check whether task-based learning within the

communicative approach framework is enough to promote positive feelings to learners who have never studied a foreign language.

The communicative approach to language teaching is broadly accepted and used in most English courses in Brazil. Often adapted, the teachers and pedagogical coordinators of such courses have the freedom to build methods based on the approach. According to Nunan (2004), communicative language teaching can be considered a philosophical approach to language learning as it comes from areas such as sociolinguistics, anthropology, psychology and sociology.

Brown (2007) writes about language as a system whose main function is to make interaction and communication possible – language, therefore, expresses meaning. That is why the communicative approach to teaching a foreign language should evolve around activities that involve meaningful communication towards the needs of the learners. Nunan (2004) also writes on language as a tool for communication rather than a set of phonological, grammatical and lexical items to be memorized.

Learning a language for real life communication, according to Brown (2007), can be achieved by providing students the necessary tools for them to develop linguistic fluency in a cooperative environment where interaction is the key to learning. The author offers six points to better determine communicative language teaching:

- Goals are focused on grammar, discourse, function, sociolinguistic and strategy – all of the

components required for communicative competence;

- Techniques are designed for the actual and authentic use of language for meaningful purposes;
- Use of language is the most important part. Therefore, fluency and accuracy are only complementary;
- Language learned in the classroom has got to be usable in real life contexts;
- Students have opportunities to reflect on their own pace of learning and develop their own learning strategies;
- The teacher plays the role of a guide.

It is sought through the communicative language teaching approach effective communication, comprehensible pronunciation, fluency and use of acceptable language – all of those aiming at creating bonds and meaning in real life; arousing the students' interest in speaking the language (with the use of different devices if necessary). As meaning is the most essential part of communicative language teaching, Brown (2007) confirms that task contextualization is a basic premise to effective communication.

According to Brown (2007), foreign language teaching cannot be followed step-by-step by a set of principles as it is composed of a dynamic approach which the teacher is supposed to change based on his or her experiences – as the professional teaches, takes risks, researches and learns, he or she becomes able to understand better the processes of language learning and how to develop tasks according to the success or failure experimented beforehand. For developing tasks in this context, task-based language learning provides the necessary designs and methodologies for the communicative approach to be effective.

TASK-BASED LANGUAGE LEARNING

In order to understand task-based language learning, firstly we have to understand the concept of task. According to Brown (2007), a task in language teaching is an important element on how to design a

class and how to assess students in both English as a Second Language (ESL) or English as Foreign Language (EFL) learning. Task-based teaching is brought upon the communicative language teaching framework as you consider a few pedagogical purposes while planning a class, such as pointing language to real world contexts, contributing to communicative goals, designing elements carefully, specifying objectives and engaging learners in problem-solving activities (Brown, 2007).

Nunan (2004) points out that a task in this context could be all the things people do in their everyday life, such as painting a fence, filling out a form or buying a pair of shoes; even though some of these outcomes may not include direct language usage. The author defines a pedagogical task as pieces of classroom work, as it:

“[...] involves learners in comprehending, manipulating, producing or interacting in the target language while their attention is focused on mobilizing their grammatical knowledge in order to express meaning, and in which the intention is to convey meaning rather than to manipulate form. (NUNAN, 2004)”

The tasks in an EFL classroom have to be complete, with a beginning, middle and an end. By doing so, students are able to notice their own learning processes, develop their own learning strategies, reflect on the outcome of a task, make decisions about what to do and how to do it and realize they need to play a new role – a role of responsibility for their own learning.

As the objective of this paper is to evaluate the emotional challenges faced by beginner English learners that left school long ago or before completing elementary education – we will get to know who the students are onwards – in an Task-Based Language Learning environment, on the next chapter we will discuss experience and its levels in order to understand how emotions can influence it.

After analyzing the experiment, it will be possible to view insights about which emotions are affecting the situation of learning so that it enables future studies in

order to consider the best approach to foreign language teaching.

In order to better understand the experiment given, it is essential to comprehend concepts regarding experience, emotions and emotional experience.

EXPERIENCE

According to McLellan (2000), our economy tends to become experience-based after going through a service-based phase. In this context, we can explain experience as a process in which the participant is involved, where the level of experience depends on the mode of participation and the type of connection of the user during the experience. The mode of participation corresponds to the *activeness* or *passiveness* of the participant and the types of connection that could be made can be internal (*absorption*) or external (*immersion*) (Pine and Gilmore, 1998).

According to the authors, these characteristics can form polarities of kinds of experience that can be engaged from the polarities previously mentioned, named The Four Realms of an Experience and represented below:

Figure 1: The experience realms (Pine and Gilmore, 1998)

McLellan (2000) explains that, in the *esthetic* experience, users are influenced by what they see, smell or hear, as it is essentially a contemplative moment with low interaction levels. The *escapist*

experience provides immersion and depends on the atmosphere where it is located, allowing more interaction than the previous type and so becoming *active* participation

The *educational* experience is essentially an active one, as it requires full attention and participation of the learner. There is need of engagement, interest and effort to connect the given information. And, finally, the *entertainment* experience consists of the *passive* aspect and happens by holding the audience's attention to present ideas, making it possible for the listeners to explore their knowledge and abilities (McLellan, 2000).

Both *educational* and *entertainment* experiences are fundamental to analyze the experiment proposed in this article. The *escapist* and *esthetic* ones follow as complementary and necessary to achieve what McLellan (2000) calls the sweet spot. In other words, the learner, in order to have a complete, rich and memorable experience, needs to have elements from the four types of experience. The sweet spot concept could be considered similar to the concept of flow presented by Csikszentmihalyi (1997), who states that the more natural the experience seems, the better it will be in terms of creating meaning and significance to the user.

When the point of conversion is reached, experience tends to provide memories to the participant. The English class prepared for this experiment should provide elements from the other quadrants in order to become 'complete' and memorable.

EMOTIONS

Emotion is a central component in human experience, which is caused by the interpretation of our everyday life events. Therefore, emotions depend on our cognition, the learning process that interacts with the external world to bring information to the internal world. According to Hoffart (2008), emotions can be seen as a quite abstract property of human functioning as it could be related to judging people, things and environments.

Hoffart (2008) sees cognition and emotion as complementary aspects for experience:

“In action theory, mind is often considered as governing as the body, and emotions are reduced to bodily reactions reflecting the state of cognition. In experience theory, the body is central while cognition is regarded as a context for emotional experiences, in the way that emotions stimulate cognition with memories and meaningful experiences.” Whereas both approaches discuss the relation between emotion and cognition, whether one dominates the other or the contrary, it is essential to see them as complementary perspectives.” (Hoffart, 2008)

The cognitive perspective defines emotions by stating that they have a function that is to help in adapting behavior (Hoffart, 2008). Desmet (2002) also points out the basic differences in classifying emotions into “the distinction between affective states and non-affective states and the distinction between emotion and types of affect”, being affect all subjective state that can be considered valenced—positive or negative. We can provide examples of valence such as like and dislike, love and disgust, fear and desire, pride and despair.

EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE

Experience when related to a product or a service could be classified into three types: aesthetic, of meaning and emotional (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). For the purposes of our study, we believe that emotional experiences are more relevant and will, therefore, be taken into further consideration.

In order to understand emotional experiences, it is of utter importance to comprehend the appraisal theory, which according to Desmet and Hekkert (2007), can be defined as the pleasant responses to products or services. It is considered that designed experiences that are consumed help building up and reinforce consumers’ identities. They don’t need necessarily to be related to the market, since experience is naturally acquired in people’s daily lives and the consumer completes it at the moment of the experience itself, generating an emotional response.

A hedonic consumption experience, on the other hand, “arouses emotional, sensorial, imaginal, and cognitive consumer’s response” (Carú and Cova,

2007) and could be considered to be every kind of performance – such as an English class.

In order to explain how the class was planned according to the EFL teaching frameworks explained beforehand and how data collection and analysis were, a brief explanation of the methodology used follows.

METHODOLOGY

CLASS PLANNING AND TEACHING

The tasks planned for this class were based on the principles of Task-Based Language teaching within the Communication Language Teaching framework. It was chosen so as it is the approach used in most English courses in Brazil and requires the learners’ constant participation to be accomplished. For the accountability of the class, we have decided on doing rehearsal rationales, which can be considered the final task that wrap-up the activities. It involves, according to Nunan (2004), role-plays, simulations, problem-solving activities and it is designed to activate their language skills (grammar, vocabulary and overall structure built over previous tasks). The class was divided into the following steps, set by Nunan into tasks, the skills involved, macrofunctions (general) of the task, microfunctions (specific) of the task and grammar involved. The speaking activities are marked and will be explained afterwards:

TASKS	SKILLS	MACROFUNCTIONS	MICROFUNCTIONS	GRAMMAR
Watch the video and tell the words you already know.	Listening	Socializing	Greetings	Greetings
Watch the video one more time and fill in the blanks	Listening, reading and writing			
Watch the movie segment with the sound off and tell if it's the first time the characters meet.	Context comprehension		Meeting for the first time, exchanging personal information	Greetings, information questions and how to answer them
Watch the movie segment one more time with the sound on and tell why you know the characters are meeting for the first time	Listening			
Watch the movie segment one more time and fill in the blanks	Listening and writing			
How do you say... / What's the meaning of... - on the board	Grammar and vocabulary			
Repetition of structures - open group	Speaking			
You've met Sarah on MSN. Fill in the blanks with the words in the box and build the dialogue.	Writing			
Rehearse the dialogue in pairs	Speaking			
Present the dialogue to the class	Speaking			

Table 1: Task-based language class functions. Adapted from Nunan (2004).

DATA COLLECTION

The main goal of this study was to check on how beginner students who were part of the experiment felt while learning a foreign language. For that to be achieved, it was necessary for them to get involved in the experience as much as possible so that, afterwards, they would open up about the class and their participation in it. Therefore, we have decided on doing in-depth interviews as we considered we would gather the data we wished for.

One of the advantages noticed was that the interview did not impose that the interviewee knows how to read or write in their mother tongue, which in our case seemed relevant as our focus group consisted of eight workers (cleaning crew) with low educational and low-income backgrounds. In addition to that, the interview made it possible for us to register body language, voice tone and other kinds of expression that would be impossible to notice through other kinds of data collection tools.

INTERVIEWS

As the main goal of the interviews was to collect data regarding the learners' feelings and emotions towards the experience of learning a foreign language, we felt it was necessary to guide the interviewees to openly talk about how each of the tasks had affected them during class. For that reason, we decided on doing a focus interview, which is open and spontaneous, without following any kind of structure, but still focusing on a specific theme.

We thought it was important to, firstly, talk to the interviewees about the nature of the research and assure them that personal information would be kept private.

Reactions

The learners were divided into two groups and were interviewed by two researchers. They began by stating how they felt by learning English for the first time. We could notice feelings of optimism, happiness, satisfaction and cheerfulness as they stated reactions such as "it is a dream come true for me, my dream was always to speak English".

Feelings of embarrassment, nervousness and fear showed especially regarding the oral tasks, in which the learners would laugh each time they were asked to speak:

- I get nervous, I can't speak
- I got embarrassed, I was afraid I couldn't speak properly. At school, I was afraid too, the teacher wasn't angry, but I was afraid.
- I didn't want to speak, but the teacher made me do so. I was scared, nervous and then I relaxed, I felt happy and wanted to keep on speaking English.

Besides noticing a small amount of positive feelings, negative responses started to arise more frequently than we expected. When asked about how those emotions of embarrassment and sadness had started, we were able to notice that a set of negative experiences in upscale environments – such as humiliation, bad work conditions and prejudice - were responsible for adverse reactions in a new environment.

We decided on exploring their past experiences in order to try and understand how it affects new experiences.

As all of the interviewees had gone through negative experiences in the past - that we believe are now responsible for their negative feelings in a new experience -, it was part of the interviewer's job to understand the reasons behind such reactions "by creating a sense of involvement and caring in the interview, the interviewer is able to get below to respondent's surface reasons and rationalizations to discover the more fundamental reasons underlying the respondent's perceptions and behavior", (Reynolds and Gutman, 1998). The connection between negative feelings and the fear of the new brought up by past negative experiences was clear.

DATA ANALYSIS

CONTENT ANALYSIS

As for the content analysis, a few different considerations take place. Through the interview not only answer analysis was considered, but also a whole set of responses regarding content. During the

class, the researchers perceived reactions during each of the tasks, such as body language, intonation and physical response after the learners were asked to do certain tasks. It was noticed, as mentioned, a strong negative reaction towards the oral activities – the learners would start laughing and denied speaking -, which was also a recurrent point during the interviews. Strong use of disappointment language was noticed when talking about being in an awkward environment where people would not talk to them or treat them as equals.

Classification of emotions

To categorize the experience analyzed in the interview, we have decided to classify the emotions using the tree-structures list of emotions defined by Parrott (2001) in which he divides emotions hierarchically into six different categories: *love, joy, surprise, anger, sadness* and *fear*. Each of these emotions contains secondary and tertiary levels according to an experiment conducted by the author.

We have, therefore, analyzed the content in its general state and categorized it into eight levels of tertiary emotions: *disappointment, embarrassment, insecurity, hope, anxiety, satisfaction, triumph* and *nostalgia*, as displayed on the samples in the table below:

Emotion	Sample	Emotion	Sample
Disappointment	"I always said I would speak English before I died, but I never had the opportunity to do so"	Embarrassment	"If some stranger comes and says 'you're doing it wrong' I get embarrassed"
Insecurity	"I have to deal with people like you, professors, doctors"	Hope	"I liked speaking English, [in the future] I could teach other people too."
Anxiety	"I feel anxious [...] it's my first time trying to speak this language, I've never done it before"	Satisfaction	"This class meant the world to me"
Triumph	"I'm glad, even speaking wrongly, but a few words came out"	Nostalgia	"I feel like a child sitting here"

Table 2: categorization of content of the EFL class into tertiary emotions. Adapted from Parrott (2001).

For our purposes in this article, we have decided on not taking nostalgia into account, as it is a very general term that involves several negative and positive emotions.

For the next step, we have consulted Parrott's system of classification of emotions in order to get the primary emotions according to the table above.

Figure 2: Tree-structured classification of emotions according to the data collected. Adapted from Parrott (2001).

From the classification above, we were able to notice how *sadness* and *joy* are the main emotions shown by the learners. As they are valenced emotions, we have decided on analyzing how such polarity could be activated.

EMOTION ACTIVATION

Izard (1993) writes about how emotion-activated systems can operate and be influenced by different situations, even though emotion activation theories are focused mainly on cognitive processes. According to the author, cognition is defined as dependent of experience-based memories, which does not include everything necessary for information processing to lead to emotion. Emotion activation could be considered the result of interaction between many types of information, involving implicit and explicit memories and how it influences on conscious processes (Izard, 1993).

According to Izard (1993) a model of emotion activation could begin on the information-processing continuum where learning and experiences state mental representations and memory to compare processes and discrimination. The author also states that it is reasonable to believe that an emotional experience can be considered a motivational condition that is manifested as action readiness, action tendency, perception, perceptual-cognitive processes or even a feeling state.

It was clear in our interviews that the sociocultural context (low income and low educational background) compared to language acquisition and environment (new and familiar) had a strong influence in activating emotions. Russel (1991) notes that affective

(emotional) states are related to each other systematically, organized in a bipolar dimension, clear in our analysis in the axis of *joy* and *sadness*.

According the author, these two dimensions when representing emotions might be activated through degrees of arousal:

“If there are only two dimensions in the cognitive representation of emotions, one might wonder about the ability of such a representation to define the myriad of affect terms such as anger, anxiety, depression, elation, and the rest that are not synonymous with either pleasure displeasure or degree of arousal. Russell and Pratt (1980) examined this question in the context of the affective qualities attributed to places (relaxing places, gloomy places, etc.) and found that, indeed, many affect terms were not synonymous with (did not cluster about) the pleasantness or arousal axes. (Russell, 1991, p. 1163)”

We have, therefore, obtained two bipolar levels of pleasantness – *joy* and *sadness* – but two different aspects of activation.

The first being the environment, in which the learners felt uncomfortable during the experience for it is too different from their regular environments, surrounded by people they feel anxious around. The second being the oral exposure they were submitted to during the tasks (as seen in Table 1). Even though tasks using different skills were applied, in our interviews only the oral ones brought up feelings of shame and sadness.

To better illustrate the designed wheels of emotion activation, we have used Russell’s circumplex model of representation. For the environment model, we used the previous mentioned emotion polarities – *sadness* and *joy* – along with qualifications of the environment – *familiarity* and *strangeness*. In order to arrange the hierarchical tree of emotions into the map, we have divided the tertiary emotions according to the set they represent along with a small description.

Figure 3: circumplex model representing emotion activation around the environment. Adapted from Russell (1980)

As for the tasks themselves, as previously mentioned, there was a high rate of feelings towards the oral tasks. As the oral tasks were divided into open group (where the learners had to come up with answers openly exposing themselves to the group) and in pairs (where the learners were able to practice along with a partner), we came up with a circumplex model regarding the activation through the speaking activities.

Figure 4: circumplex model representing emotion activation towards the speaking tasks. Adapted from Russell (1980)

Differently from the writing tasks, the oral tasks triggered mostly emotions of sadness regarding embarrassment, represented physically by laughter and denial of completing the required tasks. Emotions of embarrassment, insecurity and disappointment were highly noticed by the data analysis either in the closed and open group tasks.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

English learning could be difficult enough for the language itself, but it could be even more challenging if we consider everything that surrounds the learner: new knowledge, new environment, background history, trauma, hopes and dreams. Throughout this research, we were able to perceive how much language acquisition is worth for the senses of inclusion and belonging.

During the interviews, we were able to notice how free they were to state how they felt by learning English for the first time. We could notice feelings of optimism, happiness, satisfaction and cheerfulness among feelings of shame, sadness and insecurity. Even though it was quite hard to differentiate some of the feelings from one another, we were able, through analyzing the content, notice that some emotions were actually mixed and should not be torn apart.

The final map shows how much these feelings could be mixed. If we check only the negative side (left side of the circumplex), fear is a constant value even when represented by a set of other feelings:

- **EMBARRASSMENT/INSECURITY:** fear of not obtaining knowledge or not showing improvement in a new environment (environment);
- **DISAPPOINTMENT:** fear of disappointing or not showing improvement to other in their familiar environment (environment);
- **EMBARRASSMENT/INSECURITY:** Fear of not obtaining knowledge or not showing improvement to the group or to the teacher (oral skills);
- **DISAPPOINTMENT:** Fear of disappointing or not showing improvement to the task partner (oral skills).

As our economy is becoming experience-based (McLellan 2000), negative effects of the experience could be eased by providing scenarios of absorption in the classroom (see Figure 1). The environment, playing a passive role in the experience, is seen inside of the passive participation, or as McLellan (2000) puts it, as entertainment. In this scenario, learners do not modify the environment and cannot change their experience with it. Passive participation, on the other hand, goes against all means of the communication language teaching framework, as it demands students to participate, modify reality and freely create.

Speaking tasks, on the other hand, can be considered active participation, as it is mostly part of the learners and of the teacher to make the outcome happen. Through constant interaction, learners are able to work with real life situations and turn the language their own for a moment.

Even though there are negative emotions in both of these spheres, the results found in this research could be used to check how to ease them in the future. Based on the emotions and descriptions found on the left side of the circumplexes, a new study could explore changes in approaching oral tasks and environment in order for them to reach the sweet spot suggested by McLellan (2000). By merging entertainment, education, esthetic and escapism, along with the basics of the communicative approach, would such negative emotions be eased? If so, in a quantitative analysis, how would the same kind of group respond to the changes in language teaching approach?

When we take the environment into consideration, it is correct to say that shame, insecurity and disappointment point to lack of trust or control caused by trying to understand a different language in an already contextualized situation (Norman, 2004). Facing such issues, Design can offer solutions when it can ease, transform or exchange troublesome factors by positive ones; providing positive experiences.

Norman (2004) confirms that there are three designerly levels: visceral (connected to appearance), behavioral (connected to pleasure and easy use) and

reflexive (related to self-image, personal satisfaction and memories). Design projects can reach students at their reflexive level as they become able to check how much they learn and improve, helping them memorize the steps taken and reflect on their own progress by co-creating their own learning environment and framework according to their needs and hopes. Through collaborative planning of the processes, students would be more aware of their role as learner, allowing them to connect and identify themselves with the learning process. That way, while the teacher works as a mediator, Design acts as a medium to make the process visible (Norman, 1988). By doing so, feelings of satisfaction emerge when tasks are accomplished.

We believe that the Design field might aid the previously mentioned issues by supporting the advanced research on language teaching and learning. Works on building beginner courses for positive emotions through Design could change the scenarios presented here and provide students with a more hopeful and happier learning experience.

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